

Liming modifies greenhouse gas fluxes from soils: A meta-analysis of biological drivers

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ABSTRACT

Acidic soils cover about 30% of the world's land. Liming is a management practice applied worldwide to reduce the negative effects of acidification on soil fertility and plant growth. Liming also affects the biotic and abiotic soil properties controlling the production and consumption of the greenhouse gases (GHGs) carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and methane (CH₄). Although our understanding of how liming regulates net GHG emissions is increasing, the impact of liming on soil biological drivers of GHG emissions has not been quantitatively synthesized. Here we conducted a global meta-analysis using 1474 paired observations from 124 studies to explore the responses of GHG emissions to liming, with a focus on soil biological factors. We show that the N₂O mitigation capacity of liming could be linked to (i) increases in bacterial abundance of N₂O reductase genes (*NosZ*) and decreases in fungi:bacteria ratio, both contributing to a lower N₂O:N₂ product ratio of denitrification; and (ii) reductions in soil mineral nitrogen (N) via stimulation of plant N uptake. The limited evidence available indicates that liming reduced CH₄ emissions and the abundance of methanogens, but it had no effect on CH₄ uptake and abundance of methanotrophs. Liming-induced increases in soil CO₂ emissions can be explained by higher heterotrophic and/or autotrophic respiration. The strong coupling between liming effects on GHG emissions and on soil microbial communities involved in GHG production and consumption can be used to identify strategies to reduce GHGs in response to liming, and to improve process-based models for better predictions of soil GHG emissions.

1. Introduction

Acid soils, with pH values below 5.5, cover 30% of the ice-free land area and 40–50% of the arable soils worldwide (von Uexküll and Mutert, 1995). Soil acidification has adverse impacts on soil fertility and plant growth since low soil pH can cause nutrient deficiencies of, e.g., phosphorus (P), magnesium, and calcium, and increase the solubility and toxicity of aluminum, manganese, and iron (Fenn et al., 2006). Liming materials such as limestone and dolomite neutralize protons (H⁺ ions) in

soils, and therefore they are applied in many places around the world to increase soil pH and improve plant productivity (Fageria and Nascente, 2014; Goulding, 2016). Since soil pH is a master variable controlling soil biotic and abiotic processes, including production and consumption of greenhouse gases (GHGs), liming in turn affects the net fluxes of soil GHGs. A recent meta-analysis showed that, on average, liming reduces soil nitrous oxide (N₂O) and methane (CH₄) emissions, but increases carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from soil respiration (Wang et al., 2021).

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Our understanding of how liming-induced changes in GHG emissions vary with abiotic factors (e.g., soil texture, carbon:nitrogen (C:N) ratio, and P availability) as well as management practices, such as liming materials and rates, is growing (Wang et al., 2021; Liang and Elsgaard, 2021). Yet, the importance of soil biological properties in modifying the effect of liming on soil GHG fluxes has not been quantitatively synthesized. Microorganisms are the main biogenic sources and sinks of soil GHG emissions (Conrad, 1996; Baggs, 2011), and therefore synthesizing knowledge on key soil microbial responses to liming is crucial to develop GHG mitigation strategies.

Liming can affect the main biogenic sources of soil N₂O emissions, i.e. ammonia oxidizing and denitrifying microorganisms (Baggs and Philippot, 2011). For instance, liming can reduce N₂O emissions because acid soils promote a high N₂O:N₂ product ratio of denitrification, which is believed to result from impairment of periplasmic N₂O reductases (encoded by *nosZ* genes) associated with low pH (Bakken et al., 2012). Liming can also lower the dominance of fungi over bacteria (Rousk et al., 2010), which can decrease N₂O emissions since denitrifying fungi lack N₂O reductases (Rütting et al., 2013). Another largely ignored mechanism by which liming may reduce N₂O emissions is by stimulating plant N uptake, thereby reducing soil N availability for ammonia (NH₃) oxidizers and denitrifiers (Abalos et al., 2020). However, in some cases liming application does not reduce soil N₂O emissions (e.g. Šimek and Cooper, 2002; Cheng et al., 2020; Liang and Elsgaard, 2021). The reason may be that liming can increase N₂O emissions by stimulating the activity of denitrifiers and nitrifiers at relatively neutral pH, and/or by favouring ammonia oxidizing bacteria (AOB) over ammonia oxidizing archaea (AOA), since AOB produce more N₂O per mole of oxidized NH₃ than AOA (Šimek and Cooper, 2002; Hink et al., 2017).

Liming may also affect the main sources of soil CO₂ emissions (i.e., soil organic matter, plant residues and organic substances released by roots) and the two biological processes behind such fluxes, i.e. heterotrophic and autotrophic respiration (Kuzyakov, 2006). For example, liming can increase microbial decomposition rates of soil organic matter and the abundance of heterotrophic microorganisms, thereby increasing CO₂ emissions (Kunhikrishnan et al., 2016). Since liming generally stimulates plant productivity (e.g. Wang et al., 2021), soil autotrophic respiration from plant roots may also increase, and the higher return of organic C from exudates and plant residues can further stimulate CO₂ emission from soils (Abalos et al., 2020). Conversely, fungal dominance in acid soils may reduce CO₂ emissions due to the reported higher C use efficiency of fungi compared to bacteria (Strickland and Rousk, 2010; Waring et al., 2013).

The balance between microbially mediated CH₄ production and consumption (Conrad, 2007) determines net emissions of CH₄ from the soil. Methane is produced by methanogenic archaea under anaerobic conditions and is fueled mainly by acetate or H₂ + CO₂ resulting from fermentative breakdown of organic C compounds (Tokida et al., 2011; Watanabe, Takeda, and Kimura, 1999). Since the effect of liming on C availability can be negative (by long-term stimulation of organic matter decomposition) or positive (by stimulating plant C inputs), the resulting effect on CH₄ production is unclear. Methane is consumed (i.e., oxidized) by aerobic methanotrophic bacteria (Conrad, 2007), and this process is largely determined by the availability of CH₄ and O₂. Reduced activity of methanogens in response to liming could decrease the availability of CH₄ for methanotrophs, but on the other hand liming-increased plant growth may enhance O₂ transport into the rhizosphere, thus stimulating methanotrophic metabolism (Jiang et al., 2018).

Here, we conducted a global meta-analysis to synthesize the response of soil GHG emissions to lime addition. To identify the mechanisms underlying these effects, we also quantified the response of soil properties, C and N transformation rates, plant productivity, and functional gene abundances relevant to biotic GHG production and consumption.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data collection

Peer-reviewed papers were collated from Google Scholar, Web of Science, and China Knowledge Resource Integrated Database (CNKI) on experiments quantifying the response of soil GHG emissions to liming. We included both field, pot and lab studies in our analysis. To be included in the analysis, studies had to meet the following criteria: (1) the liming and control treatments were established under the same conditions to avoid confounding factors; (2) the means, standard deviations (SD) or standard errors (SE), and sample sizes of variables in control and liming treatments were directly reported or could be calculated. If data from the same experiment were reported more than once at different time points, only the latest data were selected. The database included studies from croplands, rice paddies, grasslands and forests. Since GHG emissions and nutrient cycling can differ between these land use types, we considered these as separate categories in subsequent analyses when data availability allowed for it. For example, for CH₄ fluxes, all studies reporting net CH₄ emissions were conducted on either rice paddies or grasslands, whereas all studies showing net CH₄ uptake were from croplands and forests. We also extracted data on soil chemical properties (pH, concentrations of NH₄⁺-N and NO₃⁻-N), N transformation rates (net N mineralization, net nitrification and denitrification rates, contribution of denitrification to N₂O emission (C_D)), N₂O:N₂ product ratio of denitrification, fluxes of N₂, NO and NH₃, functional gene abundances of ammonia oxidizing archaea (AOA *amoA*), ammonia oxidizing bacteria (AOB *amoA*), denitrifiers (*nosZ* and the nitrite reductases *nirK* and *nirS*), methanogenic archaea (*mcrA*), methanotrophic bacteria (*pmoA*), bacteria and fungi) and plant productivity when these data were reported along with soil GHG emissions (Table S1).

Because only few studies reported soil GHG emissions, functional gene abundances and plant productivity at the same time, we further extracted data from studies where only liming effects on functional gene abundances and plant productivity were reported, using the criteria outlined above (Table S2). All original data were extracted from the text, tables, figures, and appendices of the publications. Data from the figures were extracted using the g3data software version 1.5.1 (Novak and Zavjalov, 2018). A total of 1474 side-by-side comparisons of soils with and without liming (referred to as “paired observations” from now on) from 124 studies published before July 2020 were found. Among them, there were 275 paired observations for N₂O emission, 83 paired observations for CO₂ emission, 16 paired observations for CH₄ emission, and 18 paired observations for CH₄ uptake. Six studies reported emissions for N₂O and CH₄ simultaneously (17 paired observations), which allowed us to determine the effect of liming on the net global warming potential (GWP) of soil GHG fluxes based on a 100-year time horizon (IPCC, 2013). Soil CO₂ emissions were not included because the net ecosystem C balance (i.e., the net changes between C input and C output) in response to liming could not be determined, and therefore including CO₂ emissions could be misleading. The geographical distribution of study sites included in our meta-analysis is shown in Fig. S1. Around 90% of the study sites were located in the humid northern temperate zone, one of the two main regions with acid soils (von Uexküll and Mutert, 1995), whereas the number of observations from the humid tropics was much lower. Soils at most study sites were classified as common acidic soils, e.g., Cambisol, Acrisol, Andosol, Ferralsol, and Ultisol.

2.2. Meta-analysis and structural equation modeling

We used the response ratio (RR) to assess the responses to liming using the equation: $RR = \ln(X_t/X_c)$.

where X_t and X_c are the means of the liming treatment and control, respectively. These effect sizes were weighted by the inverse of their

variance. The weighted response ratio (RR_{++}) and its 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were generated by a bootstrapping procedure with 4999 iterations using METAWIN 2.1 (Rosenberg et al., 2000). The RR_{++} was considered significant if the 95% CI did not overlap zero. To ease interpretation, we back-transformed the effect size to percentage change with liming, i.e., calculated as $(e^{RR_{++}} - 1) \times 100\%$.

Structural equation models (SEM) were used to further understand the direct and indirect factors (pH, $N_2O:N_2$ product ratio, net nitrification and denitrification rates) influencing the response of soil N_2O emission to liming, with 36 paired observations from 10 studies (including field, pot and lab studies). Since net nitrification and denitrification rates were not available for all the paired observations, we imputed the missing data using mean values when needed, following the approach by Olinsky et al. (2003). Due to data paucity, functional gene abundances and plant productivity were not included in the SEM. Soil NH_4^+ and NO_3^- contents and net mineralization rate were also not included in our SEM because regression analysis showed that the relationship between these factors and the response of soil N_2O emission to liming was poor ($p > 0.05$). The software package AMOS version 17.1 (Arbuckle, 2008) was used to design the SEM models and calculate path coefficients, squared multiple correlations, direct and indirect effects and model fit. We assessed the conceptual model (full model) vs. reduced models by the goodness-of-fit statistics and used the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) to select among alternative models. We chose the final model with the lowest AIC value. Finally, we employed regression analyses to test the relationships between the response ratio of soil GHG emissions and potential biological drivers.

3. Results

3.1. General effects of liming on soil greenhouse gas emissions

Averaged across our dataset, liming significantly decreased soil N_2O emission by 38% ($p < 0.001$) and soil CH_4 emissions by 20% ($p < 0.05$), but it increased soil CO_2 emission by 41% ($p < 0.001$). The few observations available suggest that liming had no significant effect on CH_4 uptake (Fig. 1). The N_2O mitigation induced by liming tended to be greater for cropland and rice paddies than for grasslands and forests (Fig. S2), although this difference was not significant. Methane emissions were only mitigated in rice paddies (Fig. S2). Averaged across the

Fig. 1. The effect of liming on emissions of nitrous oxide (N_2O) and carbon dioxide (CO_2) across all studies, and on methane (CH_4) emission from rice paddies and grasslands and CH_4 uptake from croplands and forests. Error bars represent 95% bootstrapped confidence intervals (CIs). The number of observations for each variable is shown in parentheses. The effect of liming is considered significant if the 95% CI of the weighted response ratio does not overlap zero.

studies that simultaneously measured emissions of N_2O and CH_4 , liming reduced the net GWP of soil GHG fluxes by 33%, but this reduction was not significant (Fig. S3).

3.2. Liming effects on biotic and abiotic properties controlling the production and consumption of soil greenhouse gases

Averaged across the dataset (Fig. 2), liming reduced the $N_2O:N_2$ product ratio by 60% ($p < 0.01$), and increased N_2 emissions by 91% ($p < 0.001$). Liming also decreased soil NO and increased NH_3 emissions ($p < 0.05$), although the number of observations was limited ($n = 7-8$). The average pH increase due to liming was 1.41 units (CI: 0.39–2.44; relative increase: 23%; $p < 0.05$). Soil NO_3^- contents increased by 54% ($p < 0.001$) with liming, but soil NH_4^+ contents were not significantly affected. Liming increased net nitrification (+56%, $p < 0.05$) and denitrification rates (+203%, $p < 0.05$), but it did not significantly affect net N mineralization rates or the contribution of denitrification to N_2O (i.e., C_D). Liming significantly increased gene abundances of AOA *amoA*, AOB *amoA*, *nirK*, *nirS*, *nosZ*, bacteria and fungi. In contrast, liming decreased the abundance of methanogens and had no effect on methanotroph abundance, although these results were based on very few studies ($n = 2$ and $n = 8$, respectively). Overall, liming significantly increased plant yields by 19% ($p < 0.001$).

3.3. Key relationships between biogeochemical factors

Linear regression analyses showed that the response of soil N_2O fluxes to liming was positively related to the liming-induced change in $N_2O:N_2$ product ratio ($p < 0.001$; Fig. 3a), and negatively related to changes in denitrification rate, abundance of *nosZ* genes, and plant yield ($p < 0.05$; Fig. 3c-e). The response ratio of soil N_2O emission increased first and then decreased with an increasing response ratio of soil net nitrification rate ($p < 0.05$; Fig. 3b). Although based on a limited number of observations ($n = 8$), our analysis showed that there was a significant negative relationship between the response of AOB abundance to liming and that of soil NH_4^+ content ($p < 0.001$; Fig. 3f), and a positive relationship between the response of AOB abundance and that of soil NO_3^- content ($p < 0.01$; Fig. 3g). These two relationships were based on highly skewed datasets, and therefore the shape of these responses at intermediate values remains unknown.

Structural equation modelling suggested that liming-induced changes in soil pH indirectly influenced soil N_2O emission by affecting rates of nitrification ($p < 0.01$), denitrification ($p < 0.05$) and the $N_2O:N_2$ product ratio ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. S4).

4. Discussion

Liming may affect soil abiotic pathways contributing to GHG emissions (Zamanian et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2021). However, microbes are the predominant mediators of soil GHG production and consumption (Conrad, 1996; Baggs, 2011) and, to our knowledge, this is the first comprehensive synthesis of liming effects on soil biological drivers of GHG emissions. Consistent with previous analyses (Wang et al., 2021), our results suggest that liming is a powerful strategy to reduce N_2O emissions from agroecosystems and from forest soils. The response of soil N_2O emissions to liming is governed by 1) the rate of N transformation processes, and 2) the fraction of N that is lost as N_2O during these processes (Firestone and Davidson, 1989). Even though liming stimulated both net nitrification and denitrification rates, it decreased N_2O fluxes, likely by modifying the end product stoichiometry (i.e., $N_2O:N_2$ product ratio) of denitrification (Figs. 2, 3). This conclusion is supported by studies showing that the strongest liming-induced reduction in N_2O emissions was seen under conditions conducive to denitrification (e.g., Simek and Cooper, 2002).

Two possible microbial mechanisms can explain the effect of liming on the denitrification $N_2O:N_2$ product ratio. First, the post-

Fig. 2. The liming-induced change in twenty-one variables related to soil GHG emissions. Error bars represent 95% bootstrapped confidence intervals (CIs). The number of observations for each variable is shown in parentheses. The effect of liming is considered significant if the 95% CI of the weighted response ratio does not overlap zero. CD, contribution of denitrification to N₂O; AOA, ammonia-oxidizing archaea; AOB, ammonia-oxidizing bacteria; *nirK* and *nirS*, nitrite reductase; *nosZ*, nitrous oxide reductase.

Fig. 3. Relationships between the response ratio (RR) of emission of soil N₂O (RRN₂O) and those of (a) N₂O:N₂ product ratio (RRN₂O:N₂), (b) net nitrification rate (RRNet nitrification rate), (c) denitrification rate (RRDenitrification rate), (d) abundance of nitrous oxide reductase genes (RR*nosZ*), and (e) plant yield (RRYield), and between the response ratio of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (RRAOB) and (f) soil ammonium concentrations (RRNH₄⁺-N) and (g) soil nitrate concentrations (RRNO₃⁻-N).

transcriptional assembly of periplasmic N₂O reductase enzymes in denitrifiers may be impaired at low pH, increasing N₂O fluxes as a consequence of impeded reduction of N₂O to N₂ (Bakken et al., 2012). This explanation is consistent with our result that liming significantly increases *nosZ* gene abundance, which potentially enhances the N₂O reductase activity and the eventual reduction of N₂O to N₂ (Figs. 2, 3). Second, liming can also mitigate N₂O emissions by shifting the soil microbial community towards bacterial dominance. Soil fungi, which have

a competitive advantage in acidic soils (Rousk et al., 2010), can produce N₂O via denitrification, but lack N₂O reductase (Shoun and Tanimoto, 1991; Takaya, 2009; Strickland and Rousk, 2010). Our results showed that liming increased both fungal and bacterial biomass (Fig. 2), which aligns with previous studies (Bååth and Anderson, 2003; Ma et al., 2019), but such stimulating effect was stronger for bacteria. This indicates that liming may decrease the fungi:bacteria ratio and the contribution of fungal denitrification, thereby increasing the potential

for N₂O reduction to N₂.

According to the SEM analyses, liming also affects soil N₂O emissions by increasing nitrification (Fig. S4), likely by enhancing the abundance of both AOA and AOB, as well as net nitrification rates (Fig. 2). Together, these results suggest that liming increases the contribution of nitrification to N₂O emissions. Soil NH₄⁺ concentration was not significantly affected by liming (Fig. 2), probably because higher nitrification rates reduced the soil NH₄⁺ pool. Alternatively, liming may have increased NH₄⁺ loss through NH₃ volatilization, or it may have stimulated NH₄⁺ immobilization by microbial assimilation, as a result of stimulated abundance of bacteria and fungi (Fig. 2). The main implication of this finding is that NH₄⁺-based fertilizers may promote N₂O emissions from nitrification after lime application, and therefore nitrification inhibitors could be a way to lower these emissions. Combined application of lime and nitrification inhibitors could also decrease the environmental risk of NO₃⁻ leaching losses, which may result from liming alone (Vinther and Eiland, 1996). However, the impact of NH₄⁺-based fertilizers on NH₃ volatilization should be explored further, since both liming (Fig. 2) and nitrification inhibitors may increase this N loss pathway (Mkhabela et al., 2006; Lam et al., 2017).

We also found empirical evidence for an overlooked driver of liming-induced N₂O reductions: the role of plants. We hypothesized that liming can enhance plant growth and N uptake, thereby reducing soil mineral N availability for ammonia oxidizers and denitrifiers and subsequently constraining N₂O emissions from nitrification and denitrification (Mehnaz et al., 2019; Abalos et al., 2018, 2019, 2020). Consistent with our hypothesis, our results showed that liming increased plant yield and biomass production. However, liming also increased NO₃⁻ availability (Fig. 2), which seems to partially contradict our hypothesis. A closer inspection of our database revealed that a significant increase in NO₃⁻ availability (+61%) was only seen for studies conducted without plants ($n = 65$, $p < 0.001$), which can be explained by the increased net nitrification (Fig. 2). With plants, liming did not increase NO₃⁻ availability, and even tended to decrease it (-11%, $n = 11$, $p = 0.22$). This illustrates the role of plant N uptake in counteracting the stimulated nitrification caused by liming. Furthermore, N₂O reductions with liming were greater when studies of our database were conducted with plants (-53%) compared to without plants (-39%). Thus, while changes in microbial processes may represent the proximal mechanisms of N₂O fluxes as regulated by soil liming, the stimulatory effects of liming on plant growth and N uptake should be further explored. This also indicates that, in general, agronomic management practices that improve plant growth (without increasing soil N input) contribute to mitigating N₂O emissions.

Liming increased soil CO₂ emissions since it reduced the negative general effects of soil acidification on biological activity (Fig. 2). For example, liming increased the abundance and biomass of soil microorganisms, thereby promoting heterotrophic respiration. Furthermore, higher plant growth at increased soil pH stimulates autotrophic respiration from living roots and aboveground biomass (Chen et al., 2016). In turn, higher plant C inputs into the soil combined with higher microbial abundance may create a positive feedback further increasing heterotrophic respiration. Supporting the results of Wang et al. (2021), liming did not affect soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks. Therefore, our results suggest that increased C inputs may compensate for the increased soil respiration, resulting in small or no net differences in terms of SOC after lime application.

Soil CH₄ emissions and uptake are determined by the balance between CH₄ production by methanogens and oxidation by methanotrophs (Le Mer and Roger, 2001; Conrad, 2007). In cropland soils, our meta-analysis found liming had no significant effect on CH₄ uptake (Fig. 1). While CH₄ production in well-aerated cropland soils is limited, methanotrophic bacteria may use atmospheric CH₄ as an electron donor and C source and thereby contribute to CH₄ uptake (Goulding et al., 1996). However, due to the unspecificity of monooxygenases, ammonia oxidizers may also contribute to CH₄ oxidation in cropland soils, and

these two groups of microorganisms (methanotrophs and ammonia oxidizers) may respond differently to changes in pH (Page et al., 2009). Thus, while the methanotrophic population may be relatively insensitive to pH changes, the stimulating effect of liming on ammonia oxidizers (Fig. 2), and notably AOB over AOA, could have increased CH₄ oxidation (Nadeem et al., 2020). The lack of effect of liming on CH₄ uptake therefore is complex and may depend on the actual soil pH levels (Abalos et al., 2020). This knowledge gap deserves further examination in future experimental studies of microbial ecology.

We found that liming reduced CH₄ emissions in paddy soils, and this reduction coincided with lower abundance of methanogens. We propose that this is due to the stimulation of soil microbial activity and organic matter decomposition for example under fallow conditions (Jiang et al., 2018). In the long-term, increased decomposition rates will result in reduced substrate availability for methanogens if the organic matter losses are not compensated by other means, such as organic amendment applications (Neale et al., 1997; Paradelo et al., 2015; Jiang et al., 2017, 2018). Moreover, liming increased plant growth, which may stimulate O₂ transport into the rhizosphere when soils are flooded (Jiang et al., 2017). Higher O₂ concentrations can inhibit methanogenic growth and CH₄ production from flooded soils (Schrope et al., 1999; Conrad, 2007). Accordingly, lime application to paddy soils seems to be a feasible option to reduce the CH₄ production potential of the soil microbial community (Jiang et al., 2018). Yet, the effects of liming on methanogen and methanotroph microbial communities should be interpreted with caution, since the number of observations for these analyses was low ($n = 2$ and $n = 8$, respectively), and all the observations were from rice paddies. We therefore call for further research to confirm these results.

Overall, our findings have two main implications. First, we can use this new knowledge to identify strategies to reduce GHG in response to liming. For example, when NH₄⁺-based fertilizers are used after liming, nitrification inhibitors may be needed to lower N₂O emissions. Second, current leading process-based biogeochemical models such as the DeNitrification-DeComposition (DNDC) model (Li et al., 1992) represent denitrifiers as a single pool without considering the varying potential of different denitrifying communities to reduce N₂O to N₂. Therefore, including more detailed information on soil biological drivers into process-based models holds great potential for improving predictions on future GHG emissions.

Studies focused on liming and GHG emissions have been predominantly conducted in Europe, North America, and China. No observations were available from Africa, and only one from Middle and South America, which means that the humid tropics were underrepresented. Around one third of the soils in the tropics are acid (Sanchez and Logan, 1992), and more than a third of the soils in Sub-Saharan Africa are acid (Pauw, 1994). These are therefore regions with high prevalence of acid soils, and consequently the unbalanced geographical distribution of our dataset precludes drawing definitive conclusions at a global scale. Further research is needed in the humid tropics to better understand potential differences between the biological drivers of GHG emissions modified by liming in this climatic zone.

5. Conclusions

Our meta-analysis establishes clear links between shifts in biological processes in response to liming and regulation of soil GHG emissions. The N₂O mitigation capacity of liming could be attributed to a reduction in the N₂O:N₂ ratio (from altered denitrification end product stoichiometry and possibly from decreased fungi:bacteria ratio), and to an increase in plant N uptake reducing soil mineral N availability for microbial N transformation. The effects of liming on CH₄ fluxes matched the effects on the microbial CH₄ regulators, with reductions in CH₄ emissions (and methanogen abundance), and no effects on CH₄ uptake (and methanotroph abundance). Increased CO₂ emissions could be linked to higher abundance and biomass of soil microorganisms (heterotrophic respiration), higher plant growth (autotrophic respiration),

and the positive feedback between these two mechanisms.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Yi Cheng and Diego Abalos conceived and designed the study. Hui-Min Zhang, Zhi Liang, Yi Cheng and Diego Abalos collected and analysed the data. Yi Cheng, Hui-Min Zhang, Kees Jan van Groenigen, Zhi Liang, Lars Elsgaard and Diego Abalos wrote the manuscript. Jin-Bo Zhang and Zu-Cong Cai commented on the details of the manuscript drafts. Yi Cheng and Diego Abalos had the overall supervision of the project.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Data and materials availability

All data needed to evaluate the conclusions in the paper are present in the paper and/or the [Supplementary Materials](#).

Additional data related to this paper may be requested from the authors.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.agee.2022.108182](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2022.108182).

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